

Design and Characterization of Zolmitriptan Nanoparticle-Embedded Mouth Dissolving Films for Rapid Onset of Action

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ABSTRACT

Zolmitriptan, a 5-HT receptor agonist, is a second-generation triptan prescribed for the treatment of migraine attacks, with and without an aura, and cluster headaches. Zolmitriptan is a basic compound and solubility increases with decreasing pH of the solution, and shows poor solubility at intestinal pH. It is classified as high soluble and low permeable drug (BCS class III) and exhibit a low oral bioavailability of about 40% due to extensive hepatic first pass metabolism. To overcome this limitation, the present study was undertaken to formulate mouth dissolving films (MDF) containing zolmitriptan nanoparticles to achieve rapid onset of action and enhanced buccal absorption of nanosized particles, thereby improving oral bioavailability by circumventing first pass metabolism. Nanoparticle were prepared using chitosan, a biocompatible biopolymer, by ionic gelation method involving Chitosan and STPP (Sodium Tripoly Phosphate). Formulated nanosuspensions were characterized for particle size, polydispersity index and zeta potential. The influence of formulation and process parameters was investigated. MDF were prepared by solvent casting method using zolmitriptan nanoparticles and HPMC as the film-forming polymer, and were found to possess desirable physico-mechanical properties. *In vitro* release studies showed that more than 90% of the drug was released within 3 minutes from both simulated salivary fluid and 0.1M HCl. Conclusively, the present study demonstrates the development of a potentially commercially viable MDF formulation of zolmitriptan nanoparticle, which may provide rapid drug release and faster therapeutic action in the management of migraine attacks.

Keywords: Zolmitriptan, Mouth dissolving films, Chitosan nanoparticles, Rapid drug release, Nanoparticle-loaded films, Migraine therapy.

INTRODUCTION

Zolmitriptan is a second-generation triptan commonly prescribed for treating migraine attacks, with or without aura, and for cluster headaches. It selectively targets serotonin (5-HT_{1B}/5-HT_{1D}) receptors and is very effective at reducing migraine symptoms like headache pain, nausea, sensitivity to light, and sensitivity to sound. The drug is classified as BCS class III and it shows pH dependent solubility.^[1] Zolmitriptan has poor solubility at intestinal pH, leading to inconsistent dissolution and absorption. Zolmitriptan available as immediate release tablets, orally disintegrating tablets, and nasal spray formulations in doses of 2.5 mg and 5 mg. Even though it works well, zolmitriptan has limited oral availability of approximately 40 to 50%. This

limitation is mainly due to absorption issues and first-pass metabolism. Several research innovations have reported to improve the poor absorption by formulating drug as fast-dissolving oral films, drug loaded nanoparticles, nano sponges, nano lipid carrier to improve permeability, to bypass first-pass metabolism and prolong therapeutic action.^[2-4]

Chitosan is a linear, semi-synthetic amino poly saccharide that comes from the partial N-deacetylation of chitin. It is the second most abundant natural bio polymer and Chitosan is widely used in making nanoparticles due to its unique biological properties.^[5] Based on the research benefits of chitosan nanoparticles in improving permeation, along with the quick disintegration property of mouth-dissolving films, an attempt has been made to develop

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zolmitriptan-loaded chitosan nanoparticles within a mouth-dissolving film system. This combined approach should improve solubility, increase bioavailability, allow some buccal absorption, and offer a rapid onset of action for effective migraine management.^[6]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Zolmitriptan was the gift sample from Orchid Healthcare, Chennai, India. Mixed fruit flavour 148691 was kindly provided by Apex Laboratories, Chennai. Low molecular weight chitosan (extra pure, 10-150 m.Pas, degree of deacetylation 90%) and Sodium Tri poly Phosphate were procured from SRL Chem (P) Ltd and Nice chemicals (P)Ltd respectively. Hypromellose (Hydroxy Propyl Methyl cellulose ,15 cPs) and Polyethylene glycol (PEG) 400 were purchased from SD fine Chemicals Ltd, India. All other reagents and chemicals used in the study were of analytical reagent grade.

Methods

1. Drug-Excipient compatibility study

ATR-FTIR spectra of zolmitriptan, polymers used and blends were recorded using an Alpha Platinum spectrometer (Bruker, Germany) to confirm the compatibility. ATR-FTIR spectra of all the samples were recorded over a spectral region from 4000 - 400 cm^{-1} using 32 scans with 8 cm^{-1} resolution.

2. Preparation of nanoparticles

Chitosan nanoparticles were prepared by Ionic gelation of Chitosan and STPP (sodium tripoly phosphate). Low Molecular weight Chitosan (Extra pure, 10 - 150 m.Pas; degree of deacetylation 90%) was accurately weighed and dissolved in an aqueous solution of 1%v/v glacial acetic acid in a beaker with

the aid of mechanical stirrer (Remi motors -RQ- 122). A weighed quantity of Zolmitriptan was then added to the chitosan solution and mixed thoroughly until a clear solution was obtained.

The drug-chitosan solution was transferred to a magnetic stirrer (Remi magnetic stirrer-2MLH, 1200 RPM) and continuously stirred. Tween 80 was then added and mixed uniformly. Separately, an aqueous solution of 0.1% w/v Sodium tripoly phosphate was prepared by dissolving weighed quantity of STPP in distilled water. The prepared STPP Solution was added dropwise to the drug-chitosan solution using 1 ml insulin syringe (approximately 8 drops/min) under continuous stirring on a magnetic Stirrer. The pH of the resulting dispersion was subsequently adjusted to 5 - 5.5 using sodium hydroxide solution. The resulting nanoparticle suspension was centrifuged using a Remi cooling centrifuge (Model-C-24) at 4^o C and 12,000 rpm for 60 minutes to separate the nanoparticles (pellet) from the supernatant containing untrapped drug and free polymer. The obtained nanoparticles were washed with deionized water to remove any untrapped drug.^[7,8]

3. Optimization of nanoparticles

To optimize zolmitriptan-loaded chitosan nanoparticles, formulations were prepared by systematically varying key formulation and process parameters. These included the type of stirring device (mechanical stirrer and magnetic stirrer), stirring speed of magnetic stirrer (700, 800 and 900 rpm), stirring time (90, 120 and 180 minutes), acetic acid concentration (0.5% v/v and 1% v/v), the presence of stabilizer (Tween 80) and the concentration ratio of chitosan :STPP(4:1 and 2:1).^[9,10] The composition of all prepared formulations is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 - Formulation of Zolmitriptan nanoparticles

Batch code	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Chitosan: STPP	4:1	4:1	4:1	4:1	4:1	4:1	4:1	4:1	2:1
Ingredients	mg/batch								
Chitosan(mg)	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	40
STPP (mg)	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Zolmitriptan(mg)	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	120
Tween 80(ml)	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.6	0.6	0.3
% v/v of acetic acid	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1
Total volume (ml)	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	60
Stirring time (min.)	90	90	90	90	90	180	90	90	120
Stirring speed(rpm)	800	800	700	800	900	800	800	800	900

4. Characterization of nanoparticles

4.1. Particle Size, Zeta Potential and Polydispersity Index

The mean particle size, polydispersity index (PDI), and zeta potential of the prepared Zolmitriptan nanosuspensions were measured using a dynamic light scattering technique with a Zeta sizer Nano instrument (Zeta sizer Lab-Blue, Malvern Instruments Ltd., Worcestershire, UK).

4.2. Entrapment Efficiency (EE%)

The amount of zolmitriptan entrapped within chitosan nanoparticles was determined by an indirect method. A 15 ml sample of the nanoparticle dispersion was centrifuged using a REMI cooling centrifuge (Model C-24, REMI Elektrotechnik Ltd., India) at 12,000 rpm and 4 °C for 60 min. The supernatant was carefully separated and analysed for the untrapped drug. An aliquot of 1 ml of the supernatant was diluted to 100 ml with 0.1 M hydrochloric acid, and the concentration of zolmitriptan was determined using a UV - Visible spectrophotometer at 222 nm.^[11-14] The entrapment efficiency was subsequently calculated using the following equation

$$\% EE = \frac{\text{Total amount of drug} - \text{Amount of drug in supernatant}}{\text{Total amount of drug}} \times 100$$

5. Formulation development of mouth dissolving films

Mouth dissolving films of Zolmitriptan were prepared by solvent casting method. In the present research, nanoparticles were prepared using two different concentrations of Zolmitriptan (1 mg/ml and 2 mg/ml) and subsequently formulated into mouth dissolving films. To enable comparison of the physicochemical properties of these nano formulations, mouth

dissolving films containing the pure drug were also prepared.

5.1. Preparation of mouth dissolving films

Nanoparticle pellets obtained after centrifugation of nanosuspension were added to 15 ml of distilled water and sonicated using an ultrasonicator for 15 minutes. From this dispersion, 5 ml was taken, and 200 mg of HPMC was added with continuous stirring to obtain a homogeneous solution. Sucralose, mixed fruit

flavour, and PEG 400 were then added and mixed thoroughly. The solution was kept aside to allow removal of entrapped air bubbles. The prepared solution was poured into a Petri dish of 9.5 cm diameter and dried in a microwave oven at 50°C for 45 minutes. The dried film was carefully removed from the petridish, inspected for imperfections, and cut into small circular films of 3 cm diameter to deliver the equivalent dose of 2.5 mg per MDF. The samples were wrapped in butter paper and sealed in an Alu-Alu pouch.

Table 2 - Preparation of Zolmitriptan MDF

S.No.	Ingredients	Quantity / film
1.	Zolmitriptan/Zolmitriptan Nanoparticles*	25.1 mg
2.	Hypromellose (Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose 15 cPs)	200 mg
3.	Sucralose	50 mg
4.	Mixed fruit flavour 148691	0.025 ml
5.	Poly Ethylene Glycol (PEG - 400)	400 mg
6.	Distilled water to	5 ml

*Quantity equivalent to 2.5 mg of Zolmitriptan in single dose MDF

For the preparation of MDF containing the pure drug, an accurately weighed quantity of Zolmitriptan was dissolved in a minimum quantity of 1% v/v acetic acid to obtain a clear solution, and the volume was made up to 5 ml with distilled water. The remaining excipients were then added to this solution, and the films were cast following the same procedure used for nanoparticle-loaded MDF. The formulation compositions of Zolmitriptan mouth dissolving films containing nanoparticles (1mg/ml & 2mg/ml), and pure drug are presented in Table 2.

6. Evaluation of Zolmitriptan MDF ^[15-19]

The prepared Zolmitriptan MDFs were evaluated for uniformity of weight, thickness of film, disintegration time, in vitro dispersion time, surface pH, folding endurance, and mechanical properties.

6.1. Weight Variation

Each film was individually weighed on analytical balance and average weight of 3 films was found. A large difference in weight denotes the non-uniform distribution of drug in the film.

6.2. Thickness of film

The thickness of the different films was measured using a calibrated dial gauge (Baker Precision measuring instruments, China) with an accuracy of 0.001 mm. Thickness was measured by placing each film between the anvil and the presser foot of the dial gauge in 10 different locations and the average thickness was calculated.

6.3. Mechanical properties

Mechanical properties of films were evaluated by Texture analyser (TA XT plus, Stable Microsystems, UK; maximum load 50 kg). The reports of the tests were obtained directly from the software Exponent lite.

A. Burst Strength

Film burst strength is the distance to burst, which is an indicator of the flexibility of the film. Burst strength of the film was studied using 5 mm spherical stainless steel ball probe with the probe adapter which was connected to the load cell. Film supporting rig was attached to the heavy-duty platform and aligned with the ball probe to ensure the probe can move centrally through the aperture of film support rig. Before starting the test, the probe was calibrated for the distance. A circular strip film with an area of 7.07 cm² was placed in film supporting rig and moving probe reaches the surface of the film with the pre-test speed of 2.0 mm /sec. When the probe reaches the surface of the film, probe speed change to 1.0 mm/sec test speed with the trigger load of 5g and data recorded.

B. Tensile strength

Tensile strength is an indicator of toughness of film. The film formulations were cut into specimens with a width of 20 mm and a length of 60 mm. Film thickness was measured by means of calibrated dial gauge with

an accuracy of 0.001 mm at 5 different positions. Tensile strength of the film was determined with Tensile Grips (A/TG). The A/TG consists of two load cell grips. The lower one is fixed and the upper one is movable which was attached to the load cell. Before starting the test, the probe was calibrated for the distance. The test film was fixed to the upper tensile grip and load cell was tare for zero weight. Upper tensile grip moved to the preset distance of 25 mm and the test film was securely clamped to lower grip. The tensile force was gradually applied on the test film till the film broke. The parameters maintained were 1 mm/s pretest speed, 1mm/s test speed, distance target mode. Results of film samples which broke at and not between the grips were not included in calculations. The data reported is the mean of three individual determinations.

Tensile strength was calculated using the formula

$$\text{Tensile Strength} = \frac{F_{\max}}{A_{\text{film}}}$$

where 'F_{max}' is the maximum force at breakage (N) and 'A_{film}' is the initial cross-sectional area of the sample (mm²). The data reported is the mean of 3 individual determinations.

% Elongation was calculated using the formula

$$\% \text{ Elongation} = \frac{L - L_0}{L_0} \times 100$$

Where 'L₀' is the initial gauge length of the specimen (mm) and 'L' is the length at the moment of rupture (mm).

Young's modulus was calculated using the formula

$$\text{Young's modulus} = \left(\frac{F_{\text{lin}}}{A_{\text{film}}} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon} \right)$$

Where 'F_{lin}' is the force at corresponding strain of the linear section (N), 'A_{film}' is the initial cross-sectional area of the sample (mm²) and ε is the corresponding strain.

6.4. Folding endurance

Folding endurance was measured manually for the prepared films. A 7.07 cm² MDF was repeatedly

folded at 180°C angle of the plane at the same place up to 300 times, which was considered satisfactory to reveal good film properties. The number of times the film could be folded at the same place without breaking was noted for 3 films of same batch. [20,21]

6.5. Surface pH

MDF with highly acidic or basic pH causes discomfort while taking. To know the surface pH of the film, the film was placed in a petri dish and was moistened with 0.5 ml of distilled water and kept for 30 sec. The surface pH was measured by means of pH paper placed on the surface of the swollen films. The average of 3 determinations for each formulation was done. [22,23]

6.6. In vitro dispersion time

In-vitro dispersion time was measured petri dish method. A film was dropped in culture dish of 8 cm in diameter, containing 10 ml of simulated salivary fluid. 6 MDFs from each formulation were randomly selected and in-vitro dispersion time was performed. [24,25]

6.7. Disintegration time

The in-vitro disintegration time was determined using disintegration test apparatus. 6 MDFs were placed in each of the six tubes of the basket and apparatus operated with 900ml of purified water as the immersion fluid, maintained at 37 ± 2°C. The time in seconds taken for complete disintegration of the tablet with no palpable mass remaining in the apparatus was recorded in seconds. The FDA recommends a disintegration time of 30s or less for ODTs based on the USP disintegration test was taken as a limit for MDFs also. [26]

6.8. Drug Content and UOD

A film was weighed and dissolved in 50 ml 0.1 M HCl in a 50 ml volumetric flask and sonicated for 15 minutes. Then 1 ml was pipetted out and transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask and make up to 10 ml with 0.1 M HCl. Then the solution was analysed against 0.1 M HCl as blank in UV Visible Spectrophotometer at 222 nm.

6.9. In vitro drug release study

The dissolution experiment of Zolmitriptan MDF with nanoparticles was performed in simulated salivary fluid and 0.1 M Hydrochloric acid to simulate the dissolution at mouth followed by gastric environment. The dissolution study was carried out in a beaker containing 30 ml of simulated salivary fluid (pH 6.8) as the dissolution medium, based on the media proposed by Chavan DU et al. and Chandra A et al. [27-29] The medium was maintained at 37°C in magnetic stirrer with constant stirring at 100 rpm. At predetermined time intervals, a 3 ml aliquot was withdrawn and diluted to 50 ml with 0.1 M hydrochloric acid. The samples were sonicated using an ultrasonicator for 15 minutes and subsequently centrifuged (Portomin deluxe centrifuge) at 2500 rpm for 15 mins. The collected supernatant was filtered through a 0.45 µm membrane filter and analysed for drug content using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 222 nm.

The drug release study was performed in 500 ml of 0.1M hydrochloric acid using Lab India DS8000 dissolution (paddle) apparatus (Lab India Instruments Pvt. Ltd., India) with autosampler at $37 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ with paddle rotation speed at 50 rpm.^[30] At predetermined time intervals, a 5 ml aliquot was withdrawn, sonicated for 15 minutes using an ultrasonicator, and centrifuged (Portomin deluxe centrifuge) at 2500 rpm for 15 minutes. The collected supernatant was filtered through a 0.45 µm membrane filter and analysed for drug content using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 222nm.

6.10. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The surface morphology of the prepared mouth dissolving films was evaluated using a Carl Zeiss EVO 18 Scanning Electron Microscope (Germany). The analysis was performed using a secondary electron (SE) detector to obtain detailed surface images. Film samples were carefully cut into small pieces and mounted on aluminium stubs using double-sided carbon adhesive tape. The mounted samples were examined under an accelerating voltage of 10 kV. The micrographs were recorded at appropriate

magnifications to observe surface characteristics, uniformity, and distribution of nanoparticles within the film matrix.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Drug-Excipient compatibility study

Drug-excipient compatibility studies were carried out using ATR-FTIR spectroscopy to evaluate possible physicochemical interactions between Zolmitriptan and the selected excipients during nanoparticle and film formulation. IR spectra of Zolmitriptan, Zolmitriptan final blend placebo and Zolmitriptan final blend are given in Figure 1. The FTIR spectrum of pure Zolmitriptan exhibited characteristic absorption peaks at 3345.57 cm^{-1} , representing N-H stretching vibrations. A prominent C=O stretching vibration was observed at 1730.55 cm^{-1} . The peak at 2715.56 cm^{-1} corresponds to C-H stretching vibrations, while the absorption band at 1255.41 cm^{-1} is attributed to C-N stretching, and the band at 1015.01 cm^{-1} represents C-O stretching vibrations. These peaks confirm the structural integrity of pure Zolmitriptan. Minor peak broadening and intensity variations observed in blends and films may be attributed to physical interactions such as hydrogen bonding and molecular dispersion within the polymeric matrix rather than chemical incompatibility. Therefore, FTIR analysis confirms compatibility between Zolmitriptan and the selected excipients, indicating the suitability of these excipients for the development of nanoparticle-loaded mouth dissolving films.

2. Preparation of nanoparticles

The nanoparticles in this study were prepared by the ionic gelation method, which involves electrostatic interaction between the positively charged amino groups of chitosan and the negatively charged counter-ions of STPP. The formulation of zolmitriptan-loaded chitosan-STPP nanoparticles was optimized by varying both formulation and process parameters, as these factors significantly influence particle size, stability, drug entrapment efficiency, and their suitability for incorporation into mouth-dissolving films.

Figure 1 - IR spectra of Zolmitriptan, final blend placebo and Zolmitriptan final blend.

3. Optimization and characterization of nanoparticles

In the present study chitosan nanoparticles are optimized for various parameters and results are given in Table 3. The formulation prepared using the mechanical stirrer produced particles approaching the micron size range, indicating inadequate size reduction. Studies by Calvo P et al. and Gan Q et al. demonstrated that chitosan nanoparticles prepared by ionic gelation require controlled mixing, nucleation, and stabilization conditions, particularly in chitosan-TPP systems.^[31,32] Based on these observations, further optimization trials were continued using the

magnetic stirrer, with adjustments in process parameters such as stirring speed, stirring time, total volume, and polymer-crosslinker ratio to achieve nanoparticles with reduced particle size and improved uniformity.

Oudah MH et al. and Fàbregas A et al. revealed stirring speed has a significant impact on particle size reduction in chitosan nanoparticles.^[33,34] In the present research work chitosan nanoparticles were prepared using magnetic stirrer at three different rotational speed: 700 rpm (F3), 800 rpm (F4) and 900 rpm (F5). The results showed a marked reduction in particle size with increasing stirring speed,

confirming improved mixing efficiency and enhanced nucleation at higher rotational speeds.

Table 3 - Optimization of Chitosan nanoparticles

Optimization Parameters	Magnetic stirrer	Mechanical stirrer	Low stirrer	Optimum stirrer	High Stirrer speed	Extended time	0.5% Acetic acid	1% Acetic acid	2:1 ratio & 60 ml + 90
Batch code	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Mean Particle size (nm)	1158	947.5	1824	1153	498.6	271.7	805.5	424.7	122.7
Polydispersity index (PI)	0.7901	0.7212	1	0.9353	0.6939	0.5706	0.9944	0.5713	0.3487
Zeta potential (mV)	35.04	48.28	49.25	25.4	44.4	43.37	34.23	31.25	18.4

Calvo et al. reported that process variables including mixing time and stirring conditions strongly influence nanoparticle size and polydispersity in chitosan-TPP systems.^[31] The effect of stirring time on nanoparticle formation revealed a significant reduction in particle size with increased stirring duration from 90 to 180 minutes. Correspondingly, the polydispersity index decreased from 0.9353 to 0.5706, suggesting improved but still broad particle size distribution. The zeta potential increased from +25.4 mV to +43.37 mV, indicating enhanced electrostatic stabilization due to better chitosan-TPP crosslinking. Naghi Zadeh Khezri FA et al. demonstrated in his research that incorporation of Tween 80 as a surfactant during nanoparticle preparation provides steric stabilization.^[35] Similarly, Elmowafy M et al. reported that Tween 80 enhances the wettability of hydrophobic drug particle surfaces, thereby increasing the activation energy barrier and preventing particle aggregation. The same study also observed that formulations containing Tween 80 required longer milling time to achieve smaller particle sizes during nanosuspension preparation.^[36]

Sukmawati A et al. revealed that the addition of Tween 80 during nanoparticle preparation significantly reduced the particle size of chitosan nanoparticles to the nanoscale range. Specifically, the addition of 0.5% v/v Tween 80 produced smaller particles compared to 1% v/v, suggesting that Tween 80 acts as a stabilizing agent by reducing surface energy and inhibiting crystal growth. The

incorporation of Tween 80 (0.5%) significantly influenced the characteristics of chitosan nanoparticles prepared by ionic gelation.^[37] The mean particle size decreased from 1153 nm to 424.7 nm, indicating that Tween 80 effectively reduced interfacial tension and limited particle growth. The concentration of acetic acid significantly influenced the formation of chitosan nanoparticles. Increasing the acetic acid concentration from 0.5% to 1% resulted in a marked reduction in particle size from 805.5 nm to 424.7 nm and a decrease in polydispersity index from 0.9944 to 0.5713, indicating improved nanoparticle formation and size uniformity. This effect can be attributed to increased protonation of chitosan amino groups at higher acid concentration, leading to enhanced polymer solubility and stronger electrostatic interaction with triphosphate.

Georgieva D et al. developed mouth dissolving films of galantamine-loaded chitosan nanoparticles with 2:1 ratio of chitosan: STPP and reported high encapsulation efficiency and rapid dissolution.^[38] Based on this evidence, further trial taken with 2:1 ratio of chitosan: STPP. From our optimization it was observed increasing stirrer speed and stirring time significantly reduced particle size. Further enhance mixing efficiency in the magnetic stirrer, the total processing volume was reduced from 120 ml to 60 ml, the stirring speed was increased from 800 rpm to 900 rpm, and the stirring time was extended from 90 to 120 minutes. Particle size distribution, zeta potential

and polydispersity index of zolmitriptan nanoparticles(F9) are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Particle size distribution, zetapotential and polydispersity index of zolmitriptan nanoparticles (F9)

The optimized conditions produced a substantial reduction in particle size from 424.7 nm to 122.7 nm, along with an improvement in the polydispersity index from 0.5713 to 0.3487, indicating a more uniform particle size distribution. This improvement is attributed to the increased crosslinking density at a Chitosan: STPP ratio of 2:1, enhanced mixing efficiency due to reduced processing volume, and increased shear forces generated by higher stirring speed and time. These factors collectively promoted rapid nucleation, minimized particle growth, and prevented aggregation, resulting in stable nanosuspensions with desirable physicochemical characteristics.

Although the zeta potential was moderate (+18.4 mV), the formulation remained stable due to steric stabilization provided by Tween 80, which forms a hydrated barrier preventing particle aggregation. Studies by Wang Y et al and Elmowafy M confirmed that Tween 80 can stabilize the nanosuspension via

steric mechanisms. For nanosuspensions stabilized via only electrostatic repulsion, physical stability can be obtained with a minimum zeta potential value of ± 30 mV. However, when the electrostatic repulsion mechanism is combined with the steric stabilization mechanism, a zeta potential value of nearly 20 mV is adequate to completely stabilize a nanosuspension system.^[37,39]

3.1. Entrapment Efficiency

Initial trials were carried out without tween 80, using 40 mg of drug in total formulation volume of 120 ml at a stirring speed of 800 rpm and in drug : chitosan ratio of 1:2. The encapsulation efficiency (EE%) of these formulations was found to be in the range of 68.5% - 72.3%, corresponding to 27.4 mg - 28.9 mg of drug loading for batches F4 and F6, respectively. To determine the maximum loading capacity of chitosan nanoparticles, further trials were conducted with tween 80 as stabilizer. Higher drug

concentrations of 1 mg/ml and 2 mg/ml of were used in a total volume of 60 ml at an optimized stirring speed of 900 rpm and in drug: chitosan ratio of 1.5: 1 and 3:1 respectively. Although the chitosan concentration was reduced, the presence of stabilizer and optimized formulation parameters were found to increase the drug loading. The 1 mg/ml and 2 mg/ml formulations showed drug loading of 33 mg (55.2% EE) and 48 mg (40% EE), respectively.

4. Preparation and evaluation of mouth dissolving films

Mouth dissolving films (MDFs) were prepared using Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose (HPMC 15 cps) as the film-forming polymer by the solvent casting method. Initial placebo trials were carried out using glycerine and polyethylene glycol as a plasticizer. The MDF formulated with glycerine exhibited poor flexibility and were difficulty in removal from the petri dish. In contrast, the films prepared using polyethylene glycol were smooth, flexible, and easily peelable films with acceptable mechanical strength. For comparative evaluation, a mouth-dissolving film containing pure Zolmitriptan was also formulated.

5. Evaluation of zolmitriptan MDF

The physicochemical characteristics of Zolmitriptan MDF formulations are presented in Table 4.

5.1. Weight variation and thickness of film

The weight of the films ranged from 26.6 ± 0.17 mg to 54 ± 0.28 mg with low standard deviation values, indicating uniform distribution of drug and excipients in all formulations. The low variation in thickness confirms uniform casting and consistent film formation.

5.2. Mechanical properties of film

Among the prepared films, pure drug film showed the least burst strength, whereas films containing nanoparticles (2 mg/ml) exhibited the highest burst strength. The results of tensile strength indicate that the zolmitriptan Nanoparticle films exhibited greater strength compared to films containing pure drug. An increase in % elongation indicates that the material has become more flexible and ductile. Among the films, an inverse relationship was observed between Young's modulus and percentage elongation, indicating that increased rigidity of the polymeric matrix reduces its ability to undergo elastic deformation. The incorporation of chitosan nanoparticle into oral film formulations significantly improves mechanical strength while maintaining adequate flexibility and optimal stiffness.

All the films exhibited a folding endurance greater than 300 folds, indicating good mechanical stability and resistance to breaking during handling. The surface pH of all formulations was within 6 - 7, suggesting neutrality and non-irritant nature to the oral mucosa.

Table 4: Physicochemical characterization of Zolmitriptan MDF

Parameters	Pure Drug MDF	Nanoparticle MDF	
		1 mg/ml	2 mg/ml
Weight(mg)	26.6 ± 0.17	50 ± 0.14	54 ± 0.28
Thickness(μ m)	31.9 ± 3.3	31.8 ± 3.4	50.9 ± 2.9
Burst Strength (N)	2.26 ± 0.46	3.05 ± 0.23	3.26 ± 0.29
Tensile Strength (Mpa)	3.05 ± 0.44	3.55 ± 0.12	3.62 ± 0.34
% Elongation	19.85 ± 2.49	32.6 ± 5.26	37.3 ± 2.92
Young modulus (Mpa)	15.36 ± 0.28	11.01 ± 1.42	10.4 ± 3.36
Folding Endurance	> 300	> 300	>300
Surface pH	7	6-7	6 -7
Invitro Dispersion Time	13 ± 1.54	15 ± 0.56	16 ± 1.2
Disintegration Time	22 ± 1.10	16 ± 0.82	18 ± 0.94
Drug Content%	99.2 ± 0.52	99.3 ± 0.57	99.8 ± 0.65
UOD	1.26	1.39	1.36

*Values represent the mean \pm SD

5.3. In vitro Dispersion Time and Disintegration Time

In vitro dispersion time and disintegration time ranged from 16 to 21 seconds, demonstrating rapid dispersion of the films in the oral cavity. Nanoparticle-loaded films showed faster disintegration compared to the pure drug MDF.

5.4. Drug Content and UOD

The drug content of all formulations ranged from 98.7 % to 100.5 %, implying uniform distribution of the drug throughout the films.

5.5. In vitro drug release study

The in-vitro dissolution study of Zolmitriptan mouth dissolving films (MDF) containing nanoparticles (1 mg/ml and 2 mg/ml) and pure drug MDF was performed in simulated salivary fluid (pH 6.8) and 0.1 M HCl to mimic oral and gastric conditions. The results demonstrated enhanced dissolution of nanoparticle loaded MDF compared to the pure drug MDF. The improved dissolution may be attributed to reduced particle size, increased surface area, and uniform nanoparticle dispersion within the film. Faster dissolution observed in 0.1 M HCl may be due to improved solubility in acidic pH along with increased surface area of nanoparticles. The comparative dissolution profiles of zolmitriptan from MDF in SSF and 0.1M HCl are presented in Figures 4(a) and 4(b), respectively

Figure 3 - In vitro drug release of Zolmitriptan MDF containing pure drug and nanoparticles in (a) simulated salivary fluid and (b) 0.1M HCl.

5.6. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM images of MDF with zolmitriptan nanoparticles are presented in Figure 4. The SEM images of the

MDF shows smooth, continuous and compact morphology with uniformly distributed spherical particles. The minor aggregation observed may be due to coalescence of particle during the drying process.

Figure 4 - SEM images of zolmitriptan MDF containing nanoparticles

CONCLUSION

The rapidly dissolving MDF incorporated with zolmitriptan nanoparticles were successfully formulated. Optimization studies confirmed that particle size and stability are highly dependent on process parameters, addition of stabilizer, and polymer-to-crosslinker ratio. Zolmitriptan nanoparticle-loaded mouth-dissolving films exhibited rapid drug release and indicating their suitability for a quick onset of action, which is desirable in migraine therapy. So, it was concluded that the intent of this research was successfully made and this patient - friendly dosage form can be made commercialize which will result in great patient compliance and a more effective treatment.

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